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Principals' Welfare Management Practices For Enhancing Academic Performance Of Senior Secondary School Students In Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined principals' welfare management practices for enhancing academic performance of senior secondary school students in Rivers State. Three research questions and three (3) null hypotheses were tested and answered in the study, respectively. The design of the study was the descriptive survey with the population of 6,893 public secondary school teachers from 291 public secondary schools in Rivers State. The sample size of the study was determined using proportionate stratified sampling technique to select 378 respondents for the study. Respondents responded to a validated instrument titled: Principals' Welfare Management Practices for Enhancing Public Senior Secondary School Students Academic Performance Questionnaire (PWMPEPSSSSAPQ)" designed by the researcher after the modified 4-points Likert scale model, with a reliability index of 0.98, obtained using Cronbach Alpha statistics. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while independent sample t-test was used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that the components of principals' welfare management significantly enhanced senior secondary school students' academic performance. It was recommended that the principal should foster a culture of continuous improvement and professional development. This is to ensure that the school is always up to date with current improvements that can be made to facilitate academic performance of students, amongst others.

Keywords: Principal, Welfare Management Practices, Academic Performance of Students

INTRODUCTION

Secondary school education plays a pivotal role in the educational landscape of Rivers State, Nigeria. It is essential for several reasons and contributes to the overall development of students, the prosperity of the state, and the nation as a whole. Secondary education serves as a stepping stone for students who aspire to pursue higher education, such as universities or technical colleges. It provides the necessary academic background, equipping them with essential knowledge and skills that are fundamental for advanced studies (UNESCO, 2019). A well-educated workforce is vital for economic development, and secondary school education in Rivers State plays a key role in this regard. It produces a skilled labor force capable of contributing to various sectors, such as healthcare, engineering, and technology, thus driving economic growth (World Bank, 2019). Completing secondary education increases the likelihood of students securing better-paying jobs, ultimately leading to an improved economic situation. This education can

serve as a pathway out of poverty for many individuals and families in Rivers State (Adeyemo & Arogundade, 2021).

Beyond academic knowledge, secondary education fosters personal growth and the development of crucial social skills. Students learn to interact with peers, manage responsibilities, and develop self-discipline, time management, and critical thinking skills (Abdu-Raheem, 2021). Secondary school education introduces students to civic education, helping them understand their rights and responsibilities as citizens. This knowledge is essential for fostering active and informed participation in the democratic process, contributing to the state's democratic health (Omotola, 2018). Schools in Rivers State are often instrumental in imparting important life skills, such as sexual education, drug awareness, and nutrition. These skills are critical for students' overall well-being (Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria, 2018). As part of Nigeria, Rivers State contributes to the national development agenda. An educated populace in the state can play a significant role in the country's progress, providing a workforce with diverse skills to address national challenges and opportunities (Nwaubani, 2022). Secondary school education in Rivers State is of paramount importance, as it serves as a foundation for higher education, fosters personal growth, contributes to economic development, reduces poverty, and promotes civic engagement. It equips students essential skills and knowledge, thereby playing a crucial role in the overall development of both the state and the nation.

The actualization of these lofty goals of secondary school education depends on the academic performance of the students at this level. Academic performance is a critical factor in determining the extent to which students can maximize their secondary school education in Rivers State, Nigeria. The link between academic performance and the realization of educational goals is well-established and has far-reaching implications for students' future prospects and contributions to society. For instance, high academic performance in secondary school is often a prerequisite for admission to higher education institutions such as universities and technical colleges. Achieving good grades and standardized test scores opens up opportunities for students to pursue advanced studies, which can lead to more diverse career choices and higher income potential (Adegoke, 2021). Exceptional academic performance can make students eligible for scholarships and financial aid programs. In Rivers State, as in other regions, various government and private organizations offer scholarships to students who excel academically. These scholarships can significantly reduce the financial burden of education and encourage students to pursue higher education (Ike, 2019).

Academic success in secondary school equips students the knowledge and skills required to access a wide range of career opportunities. Employers often consider academic performance as a measure of an individual's work ethic, commitment, and ability to learn, which can influence hiring decisions (Ikechukwu & Ikechukwu, 2019). Maximizing secondary education is not just about academic or career success; it also involves personal growth and fulfillment. Achieving high academic standards can boost a student's self-esteem and confidence, leading to a sense of accomplishment and motivation to pursue their passions and interests (Adigwe, 2019). In a highly competitive job market, academic performance serves as a distinguishing factor. Employers often prefer candidates who have excelled academically, as it suggests a strong foundation of knowledge and the ability to adapt and excel in challenging environments (Ogbonna, 2022).

The role of a principal in a secondary school in Rivers State is multifaceted and crucial to the effective functioning and overall success of the school. The principal's responsibilities encompass administrative, educational, and leadership aspects, which contribute to the attainment of the school's educational goals and objectives. Principals in Rivers State secondary schools are academic leaders. They are responsible for setting the academic direction of the school, ensuring that the curriculum is effectively delivered, and that teaching and learning standards are maintained at a high level. They play a pivotal role in fostering a culture of academic excellence within the institution (Osakwe & Uwaoma, 2019). Principals are responsible for the efficient management of the school's administrative affairs. This includes budget

management, resource allocation, staff recruitment and development, and ensuring the school complies with government regulations and policies (Eke, 2022).

Maintaining discipline and ensuring the well-being of students are central to the principal's role. Principals in Rivers State secondary schools are responsible for creating a safe and conducive learning environment where students can thrive academically and personally. They may handle disciplinary issues and promote policies related to student welfare (Federal Ministry of Education, Nigeria, 2018). Principals act as intermediaries between the school and the local community, parents, and various stakeholders. They facilitate communication, engage with parents and community members, and promote partnerships that can enhance the school's resources and support. The principal plays a role in the professional development of teachers and staff. They identify training needs, organize workshops, and provide guidance to help educators improve their teaching methods and stay updated with educational trends.

Principals are responsible for establishing and promoting the school's values and culture. They set the tone for the school's ethos, values, and expectations, creating a positive and inclusive school culture that supports students' development (Akporhonor, 2018). In handling conflicts and disputes among staff, students, and parents, the principal acts as a mediator. They work to ensure that issues are resolved amicably, creating a harmonious learning environment (Kpolovie & Sule, 2018). Principals are tasked with implementing educational policies and reforms in line with national and state regulations. They ensure that the school aligns with the educational objectives of Rivers State and Nigeria as a whole (Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council, 2022).

The principal can specifically enhance students' academic performances by utilizing several welfare management practices such as: provision of basic physical facilities, career counselling and healthcare services. School principals are expected to provide instructional leadership by setting the educational vision for the school, supporting teachers in their professional development, and ensuring curriculum alignment with state and national standards (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2019). They often engage in instructional leadership through activities such as professional development for educators and the promotion of effective teaching practices. By doing so, principals contribute to enhancing the quality of teaching and, consequently, students' academic performance.

Principals manage the day-to-day operations of the school, including budgeting, resource allocation, and the scheduling of classes and activities (Daresh, 2019). They are also responsible for the implementation of policies and procedures. Additionally, principals are responsible for scheduling classes and activities, making sure that school operations run smoothly, and that the school calendar aligns with instructional goals and standards. In their administrative role, school principals handle issues such as student discipline, staff evaluations, and communication with parents and the broader community (Gunter et al., 2022). Principals often serve as the final authority in disciplinary matters and must ensure a safe and inclusive learning environment. They also interact with teachers, staff, and parents to build a positive and supportive school community. The principal can specifically enhance students' academic performances by utilizing several welfare management practices such as: provision of basic physical facilities, career counselling, and healthcare services.

Principals can make provision of basic physical facilities, such as classrooms, libraries, laboratories, recreational areas, restrooms, and security measures, as it is crucial for enhancing the academic performance of senior secondary school students (Jibrin & Fageyinbo, 2021). Adequate classrooms, well-equipped libraries (Imam et al., 2019), and modern laboratories (Agboola, 2023) create a conducive learning environment. Additionally, recreational facilities like sports fields and playgrounds help reduce stress and improve cognitive abilities (World Bank, 2012), while clean and hygienic restroom facilities are essential to prevent health issues that can impact attendance and performance (Asiyanbola & Oyediran, 2021). School principals play a central role in ensuring the availability, maintenance, and proper utilization of these facilities, thereby fostering a conducive learning environment and ultimately enhancing academic performance.

Furthermore, by providing career counseling and allocating resources for materials, technology, and counseling spaces, principals can offer students personalized advice, develop educational plans, integrate career-related content into classroom lessons, and organize workshops that expose students to diverse career opportunities, ultimately increasing motivation and engagement (American School Counselor Association, 2020; Lapan et al., 2021). Principals can make provision of health care services towards enhancing academic performance of students. Healthcare services, encompassing medical check-ups and counseling, are integral to enhancing academic performance, with Basch's study (2011) revealing a direct connection between students' health status and their academic achievement. School principals can comprehensively address students' health needs, focusing on preventive measures, such as immunization campaigns, health education, and nutrition programs (Wang et al.2019), Additionally, prioritizing students' mental health is vital, as studies indicate that addressing mental health issues positively impacts academic performance (Patalay et al.2018).

Nevertheless, addressing challenges such as budget constraints, personnel shortages, and community resistance is crucial to the successful provision of healthcare services in schools, ultimately fostering an optimal learning environment and improving academic outcomes. Nwosu (2019) underscores that the principal's role extends beyond administration to encompass educational leadership, involving the development and implementation of strategies for enhancing academic performance through network training. Olaniyan (2021) opined that there is need for adequate principals' welfare management practices, considering how it enhances students performance. According to this scholar, principals must carefully plan and manage welfare of students to maximize their impact, bearing in mind the unique needs and conditions of each school. Tailoring strategies to meet the specific requirements of each school, such as collaboration with local authorities, community organisations, and potential funding partners, is crucial for ensuring equitable access to welfare packages for all students. Hence, it was on this premise that this study sought to investigate the extent principals' welfare management practices enhance public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Today, the student welfare services especially in the area of physical infrastructures seem to be inadequate, as some of the existing ones are dilapidated, and constitute danger to the health of the students and the entire school environment. For instance, the classrooms and hostel accommodation for boarding schools are unconducive and deplorable and this affect the academic performance of students and their all-round development. Public and researchers personal observation of classrooms shows cracked/decaying walls, sagging roofs, blown-off roofs, and bushy surroundings are common phenomenon in schools. This situation does not augur well for effective teaching and learning. Decrying the present state of physical facilities, observation also shows that there are no counseling services for students to reposition them on their career path nor deter them from wrong doings which may have a negative effect on their academic performance. In addition, sanitary welfare service seem to be absent.

In some schools it is observed that students defecate by means of 'fly over or shot put'. Fly over and shot put refer to a practice where by students defecate inside polythene bags and throw it across the fence. This is because of the poor state of the toilets as they are not fuctional for students use. Also, in the area of health care services, little or nothing is done to provide students with health care services to cater for their health when the need arise in the school. There are no sickbays in some schools, where such is claimed to exist, it is found that there no medical staff personnel and drugs available on ground for students who may be needing them. Equally water supply, electric power supply and internet network services are seen to be epileptic in most of the schools, making regular washing of hands, use of computer and internet frustrating for students to improve on their academic performance. The present state of student welfare practice is apparently affecting the students in many ways, and it will be more devastating if nothing is done to savage the situation. Hence, this situation informs the research's interest to embark on this study.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate principals' welfare management practices for enhancing public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study sought to:

1. determine the extent to which principals' provision of basic physical facilities enhance public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State.
2. examine the extent to which principals' provision of career counselling enhance public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State.
3. find out the extent to which principals' provision of health care services enhance public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were posed to guide the study:

1. To what extent does principals' provision of basic physical facilities enhance public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does principals' provision of career counselling enhance public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State?
3. To what extent does principals' provision of health care services enhance public senior secondary school students academic performance in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 alpha level.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals' provision of physical facilities enhance senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals' provision of career counselling enhance senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals' provision of health care services enhance senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey design was considered appropriate because it aid in investigating an existing phenomenon in order to explain the situation in its real form. The population of this study comprised of 6,893 teachers (3490 male and 3,403 female) in 291 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Source: Planning Research Statistics Department, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, 2023). A sample size of 378 respondents was drawn from the population of 6,893 teachers using Taro Yamane Formula. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select 6 Local Government Areas spread across 3 Senatorial District Rivers State (Rivers South-East, Rivers West and Rivers East), where respondents were drawn for equal representation. However, 79% (300) questionnaire were retrieved after the administration of the instrument. Therefore, the actual sample for the study at the end of administration was 300. The instrument used for this study a self-structured questionnaire titled: Principals' Welfare Management Practices for Enhancing Public Senior Secondary School Students Academic Performance Questionnaire (PWMPEPSSSSAPQ)", which consisted of demographic data as well as response items to address the seven research questions. The instrument was coded with modified 4-point Likert Scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4 points, High Extent (HE) = 3 points, Low Extent (LE) = 2 points and Very Low Extent (VLE) = 1point. The respondents were to tick any of this scale which suits their opinion. The instrument was validated and Cronbach alpha reliability method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument which yielded an index of 0.98. Mean and standard deviation was computed to provide answers to the research questions, while t-test was adopted to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Research Question One: *To what extent does principals' provision of basic physical facilities for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Mean of Male and Female Teachers on the Principals' provision of basic physical facilities for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

S/No.	Items/Statements	Male Teachers N=132		Female Teachers N=168		Mean Set	
		Mean X ₁	SD	Mean X ₂	SD	X ₁ X ₂	Decision
1	The principal ensures that the classrooms are furnished with desks, chairs and teaching aids to aid students learning in the classroom	3.01	0.85	3.06	0.71	3.04	Moderate Extent
2	The principal ensures that the library is well stocked with variety of books, and other reference materials for students reading/sourcing of information.	2.95	0.98	3.00	0.88	2.98	Moderate Extent
3	The principal ensures that depending on the school's curriculum, science laboratories for subjects like biology, chemistry and physics are provided for practical works.	3.10	0.99	3.32	0.75	3.21	High Extent
4	The principal ensures that computer laboratories with internet access are provided for learning and research of the students	3.54	0.82	3.55	0.76	3.55	High Extent
5	The principal ensures that sports facilities and equipments are provided for physical activities for the students	2.89	0.99	3.18	0.88	3.04	Moderate Extent
6	The principal ensures that clean and well-maintained toilets are provided for students and other members of staff.	3.23	0.98	3.48	0.83	3.36	High Extent
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		3.12	0.94	3.27	0.80	3.19	Moderate Extent

Source: Researcher's SPSS Data Output, 2024

Decision Rule: 1.00 – 1.79 = Very Low Extent (VLE), 1.80 – 2.49 = Low Extent (LE), 2.50 – 3.19 = Moderate Extent (ME), 3.20 – 4.00 = High Extent (HE), 4.00 – 5.00 = Very High Extent (VHE)

From Table 1, data show that items 3, 4 and 6 had a mean score between the range of 2.50 – 3.19 showing a moderate extent (ME), indicating that principals' provision of basic physical facilities enhanced senior secondary school students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State are moderate especially in the area of ensuring that the classrooms are furnished with desks, chairs and teaching aids to aid students learning in the classroom, ensuring that the library is well stocked with variety of books, and other reference materials for students reading/sourcing of information and ensuring that sports facilities and equipments are provided for physical activities for the students. However, there

scores in items 3, 4 and 6 were between the range of 3.20 – 4.00. This indicates that teachers agree to a high extent (HE) that principals’ provision of basic physical facilities enhanced senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State, especially in the areas of ensuring that depending on the school’s curriculum, science laboratories for subjects like biology, chemistry and physics are provided for practical works, ensuring that computer laboratories with internet access are provided for learning and research of the students and ensuring that clean and well-maintained toilets are provided for students and other members of staff.

In summary, the average mean of 3.19 (which falls within the range 2.50 – 3.19), indicates that teachers agree that principals’ provision of basic physical facilities enhanced senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a moderate extent (ME)

Research Question Two: *To what extent does principals’ provision of career counselling for enhancing senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Mean of Male and Female Teachers on the Principals’ provision of career counselling enhances the senior secondary school students’ academic performance in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

S/No.	Items/Statements	Male Teachers N=132		Female Teachers N=168		Mean Set	
		Mean X ₁	SD	Mean X ₂	SD	X ₁ X ₂	Decision
1	The principal ensures that the students have access to wide range of career-related resources, such as: job market information, university application materials, and scholarship opportunities	3.30	0.92	3.48	0.72	3.39	Moderate Extent
2	The principal ensures that students have access to information about various career paths, educational options, vocational training programmes	3.10	1.02	3.33	0.91	3.22	High Extent
3	The principal periodical organizes career fairs, inviting special guests from various professions to help students gain insight into different careers	3.11	0.98	3.32	0.92	3.22	High Extent
4	The principal supports the organization of workshops that focus on essential career development skills like resume writing, interview techniques	2.59	0.93	2.33	0.89	2.46	Low Extent
5	The principal collaborates with local businesses and organizations to establish internship opportunities for students	3.33	0.94	3.53	0.80	3.43	Moderate Extent
6	The principal ensures the school has access to online career resources and tools that student can use for self-guided career exploration	3.35	0.87	3.57	3.25	3.46	Moderate Extent
Average Mean/Standard Deviation		2.94	1.07	3.00	0.93	2.97	Low Extent

Source: Researcher’s SPSS Data Output, 2024

Decision Rule: 1.00 – 1.79 = Very Low Extent (VLE), 1.80 – 2.49 = Low Extent (LE), 2.50 – 3.19 = Moderate Extent (ME), 3.20 – 4.00 = High Extent (HE), 4.00 – 5.00 = Very High Extent (VHE)

From Table 2, data show that items 1, 5 and 6 had a mean score between the range of 2.50 – 3.19 showing a moderate extent (ME), indicating that principals’ provision of career counselling enhanced senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State are moderate especially in the area of: ensuring that the students have access to wide range of career-related resources, such as job market information, university application materials, and scholarship opportunities, collaborating with local businesses and organizations to establish internship opportunities for students, ensuring the school has access to online career resources and tools that student can use for self-guided career exploration. However, there scores in items 2 and 3 were between the

range of 3.20 – 4.00. This indicates that teachers agree to a high extent (HE) that principal ensures that students have access to information about various career paths, educational options, vocational training programmes, the principal periodical organizes career fairs, inviting special guests from various professions to help students gain insight into different careers. Inversely, item 4 had a mean score ranging between 1.80 – 2.49. This indicates that teachers agree to a low extent (LE) that principals’ provision of career counselling enhanced senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State, particularly in the area of supporting the organization of workshops that focus on essential career development skills like resume writing, interview techniques.

In summary, the average mean of 2.97 (which falls within the range 2.50 – 3.19), indicates that teachers agree that principals’ provision of basic physical facilities enhanced senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a moderate extent (ME)

Research Question Three: *To what extent does principals’ provision of health care services for enhancing senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State?*

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Mean of Male and Female Teachers on the Principals’ provision of health care services for enhancing senior secondary school students’ academic performance in Secondary Schools in Rivers State.

S/No.	Items/Statements	Male Teachers N=132		Female Teachers N=168		Mean Set	
		Mean X ₁	SD	Mean X ₂	SD	X ₁ X ₂	Decision
1	The principal ensures that staff members are adequately trained on basic first aid in the incidence of emergency for students wellbeing.	3.22	0.89	3.25	1.04	3.24	High Extent
2	The principal initiates physical fitness programs and anti-bullying programs to promote a healthy school environment for students learning.	3.18	0.95	3.35	0.85	3.27	High Extent
3	The principal coordinates health screenings for students, including vision, hearing, and dental check-ups, to identify potential health issues early on.	3.14	1.10	3.38	0.98	3.26	High Extent
4	The principal oversees school meal programs and encourage healthy food choices, ensuring that students have access to nutritious meals and snacks throughout the day	3.24	0.97	3.48	0.79	3.36	High Extent
5	The principal develops and regularly update emergency response plans, ensuring that the school is prepared to handle medical emergencies and communicate effectively with parents and local healthcare providers in case of a health crisis.	3.18	0.96	3.39	0.83	3.29	High Extent
6	The principal ensures that the students have access to guidance counsellors or mental health professionals who can provide counselling and support to students dealing with emotional, behavioural, or psychological issues.	3.21	0.92	3.29	0.93	3.25	High Extent
	Average Mean/Standard Deviation	3.20	0.96	3.36	0.89	3.28	High Extent

Source: Researcher’s SPSS Data Output, 2023

Decision Rule: 1.00 – 1.79 = Very Low Extent (VLE), 1.80 – 2.49 = Low Extent (LE), 2.50 – 3.19 = Moderate Extent (ME), 3.20 – 4.00 = High Extent (HE), 4.00 – 5.00 = Very High Extent (VHE)

From Table 3, data show that scores in items 1,2,3,4,5 and 6 were between the range of 3.20 – 4.00. This indicates that teachers agree to a high extent (HE) that principals’ provision of health care services enhanced senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State, in all the areas which include: ensuring that staff members are adequately trained on basic first aid in the incidence of emergency for students wellbeing, initiating physical fitness programs and anti-bullying programs to promote a healthy school environment for students learning, coordinating health screenings for students, including vision, hearing, and dental check-ups, to identify potential health issues early on, overseeing school meal programs and encourage healthy food choices, ensuring that students have access to nutritious meals and snacks throughout the day, developing and regularly updating emergency response plans, ensuring that the school is prepared to handle medical emergencies and communicate effectively with parents and local healthcare providers in case of a health crisis, ensuring that the students have access to guidance counsellors or mental health professionals who can provide counselling and support to students dealing with emotional, behavioural, or psychological issues.

In summary, the average mean of 3.28 (which falls within the range 3.20 – 4.00), indicates that teachers agree that principals’ provision of health care services enhanced senior secondary school students’ academic performance in public secondary schools in Rivers State to a high extent (HE).

Test of Hypotheses

Hypotheses One: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals’ provision of physical facilities enhance senior secondary school students’ academic performance in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test Analysis of the difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals’ provision of physical facilities enhance senior secondary school students’ academic performance in Rivers State.

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	z-cal	z-crit.	Remark
Male	132	3.12	0.94	298	-1.360	1.96	H ₀₁ Accepted
Female	168	3.27	0.84				

Alpha level = 0.05

Data on Table 4 show the value of z-cal. to be -1.360 while the value of z-crit. was 1.96. Since the value of z-cal. of 2.65 is less than the value of z-crit. of 1.96, the null hypothesis was accepted and this implied that there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals’ provision of physical facilities enhance senior secondary school students’ academic performance in Rivers State

Hypotheses Two: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals’ provision of career counselling enhance senior secondary school students’ academic performance in Rivers State.

Table 5: z-test Analysis of the difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals’ provision of career counselling enhance senior secondary school students’ academic performance in Rivers State.

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Remark
Male	132	2.59	0.93	298	-0.519	1.96	H ₀₂ Accepted
Female	168	2.33	0.89				

Alpha level = 0.05

Table 5 shows that the value of z-cal. is -0.519, the z-crit. is 1.96 and the chosen alpha level is 0.05. This reveals that the z-cal. is less than z-crit. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The result revealed there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals' provision of career counselling enhance senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State.

Hypotheses Three: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals' provision of health care services enhance senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State.

Table 6: z-test Analysis of the difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals' provision of health care services enhance senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State.

Gender	N	\bar{X}	SD	df	z-cal.	z-crit.	Remark
Male	132	3.20	0.96	298	-1.49	1.96	H ₀₃ Accepted
Female	168	3.36	0.89				

Alpha level = 0.05

Table 6 shows that the value of z-cal is -1.49, the z-crit. is 1.96 and the chosen alpha level is 0.05. This reveals that the z-cal. is less than the z-crit. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted. The result revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the extent principals' provision of health care services enhance senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS/IMPLICATION

The first finding of the study is that ways the principal provides basic physical facilities for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State: Ensuring that the classrooms are furnished with desks, chairs and teaching aids to aid students learning in the classroom, ensuring that the library is well stocked with variety of books, and other reference materials for students reading/sourcing of information, ensuring that depending on the school's curriculum, science laboratories for subjects like biology, chemistry and physics are provided for practical works, ensuring that computer laboratories with internet access are provided for learning and research of the students, ensuring that sports facilities and equipments are provided for physical activities for the students, ensuring that clean and well-maintained toilets are provided for students and other members of staff. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the principals' provision of basic physical facilities for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings agree with Fan and Chan (2019), Iman et al (2019), Jibrin and Fageyinbo (2021) whose studies found significant differences. . A possible explanation for these may be in fact that teaching within the fore walls of a school can only be adequately done with adequate physical facilities. These findings imply that students' academic performance is enhanced by principals' provision of basic physical facilities

The second finding of the study is that ways the principal provides career counselling for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State include: Ensuring that the students have access to wide range of career-related resources, such as: job market information, university application materials, and scholarship opportunities, ensuring that students have access to information about various career paths, educational options, vocational training programmes., ensuring periodical organizes career fairs, inviting special guests from various professions to help students gain insight into different careers, supporting the organization of workshops that focus on essential career development skills like resume

writing, interview techniques, collaborating with local businesses and organizations to establish internship opportunities for students, ensuring the school has access to online career resources and tools that student can use for self-guided career exploration. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the principals' provision of career counselling for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings do not agree with Gysbers and Henderson (2018) findings which indicated no significant difference in career counselling and academic performance of students in the area of their study. However, it agrees with the findings of Pascarella and Terenrani (2019) which found a significant difference. This finding can be due to the area of study. In developed countries they may not pay much attention to career as they would always have something to do to keep body and soul together. They may even be paid by their government to go to school until they are able to work and pay back. Whereas, in Nigeria, education is a means of escape from the clutches of poverty. Hence, students would pay attention to career counsel, including their parents. These findings imply that students' academic performance is enhanced by principals' provision of career counselling.

The third finding of the study is that ways the principal provides health care services for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in Rivers State include: Ensuring that staff members are adequately trained on basic first aid in the incidence of emergency for students wellbeing, initiating physical fitness programs and anti-bullying programs to promote a healthy school environment for students learning, coordinating health screenings for students, including vision, hearing, and dental check-ups, to identify potential health issues early on, overseeing school meal programs and encourage healthy food choices, ensuring that students have access to nutritious meals and snacks throughout the day, developing and regularly updating emergency response plans, ensuring that the school is prepared to handle medical emergencies and communicate effectively with parents, ensuring that the students have access to guidance counsellors or mental health professionals who can provide counselling and support to students dealing with emotional, behavioural, or psychological issues. Also, a corresponding finding from test of hypothesis establishes no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female teachers on the principals' provision of health care services for enhancing senior secondary school students' academic performance in secondary schools in Rivers State. These findings agree with Ogbonna (2022) and Wang et al (2019). A possible explanation for these may be in fact that one has to be healthy to be able to learn, talk more of doing well academically. Students who are sick will not be able to engage fully in academic activities like their healthy mates, so it is no surprise that provision of health facilities is linked to students' academic performance. These findings imply that students' academic performance is enhanced by principals' provision of health care services.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the discussions on them and their educational implication, it is concluded that appropriate welfare management practice that can enhance students' academic performance include (but not limited to) provision of basic physical facilities, career counselling, and health care services

RECOMMENDATIONS

In the light of the conclusion of the study, it is recommended as follows:

1. The school principal should establish clear academic goals and expectations for both teachers and students. This will serve as a blueprint or a reference point to build expectations and measure results. The principal should communicate these goals and expectations to the school community, so they can be carried along in the school activity and are aware of what to expect. Monitor progress regularly and provide feedback.
2. The principal should lead by example by providing strong and effective leadership that sets a positive tone for the school.

- The principal should foster a culture of continuous improvement and professional development. This is to ensure that the school is always up to date with current improvements that can be made to facilitate academic performance of students.

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